

Optimal Concentrations of Alkaline Electrolytes for Enhanced Green Hydrogen Production via Alkaline Water Electrolysis

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ABSTRACT

The transition from traditional fossil fuel energy to green and sustainable energy sources has heap on the demand for efficient green hydrogen production methods. Alkaline water electrolysis is safe and considered to be stands out as a mature and scalable technology for hydrogen generation. In this paperv we have analyze the effect of concentration on the production of hydrogen using electrolysis of water. Two alkalis NaOH and KOH were selected to perform the comparison of Hydrogen production via different concentration. From results it was revealed that the optimal concentration in the said research is the 2 molar KOH with small cell voltage and large current density. Finally for longer life performance, the temperature of the solution is the parameter. The temperature of KOH based system is less than the NaOH based system hence KOH with 1 molar solution gives the optimum performance in terms of hydrogen production and life of the hydrogen generator.

I. INTRODUCTION

Energy is playing a vital role in modern day life [1-2]. The demand of energy is rising day by day. A significant part of worlds electricity generation is obtained using fossil fuel. Burning fossil fuel for energy generation causes rapid decrease in their reserves [3]. Apart from their limited stocks, fossil fuel is also causing environmental issues like greenhouse gas emissions and air pollution. To compensate for the said problems, green, sustainable and renewable energy sources have been proposed. Among them, hydrogen fuel is considered as clean, efficient and low cost.

To generate hydrogen fuel, a process known as water electrolysis is used. Electrolysis of water splits water into

hydrogen and oxygen gases. The reaction requires an electrolyte. Since there is no carbon involved so the energy generated is carbon-free [4]. The main advantage of hydrogen fuel is that it generates no harmful gases. The hydrogen fuel cell technology is reported to be two to three times more efficient than conventional fossil fuel technologies. A typical hydrogen fuel cell is reported to 60% efficient compared to conventional fuel generators with efficiencies of 33% – 35% [5]. Apart from the advantages, some of the challenges in hydrogen are high over potentials, catalyst degradation, and system inefficiencies. Alkaline electrolyzers are reported to be commonly used for hydrogen production due to their low cost and the availability of alkaline electrolytes. The

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concentration and temperature of the electrolyte plays an important part in the production of hydrogen via electrolysis [6].

Proton exchange membrane (PEM) electrolyzers is another potent method which use solid polymer membranes for hydrogen generation. These systems offer compact designs, high-purity hydrogen, and high current densities but rely on expensive noble metal catalysts such as platinum and iridium. Solid oxide electrolyzer (SOE) is the third method. SOE operates at high temperatures with typical range from 700°C –1000°C. While SOEs can achieve higher efficiencies by utilizing thermal energy, they are limited by material degradation and high costs [7-8]. The generation of green hydrogen from electrolysis of water makes it viable for the transition from fossil fuel to renewable energy. Water electrolysis via alkaline water makes it safe, cost effective easily implemented technology. However, it also comes with some limitations like the type of alkaline electrolytes and their concentration which effects the efficiency and stability of the system. This research investigates the effect of concentration on and its optimization on green hydrogen production via electrolysis of water.

II. METHODOLOGY

Cell for Hydrogen generation

For Hydrogen generation, the cell design used is depicted in figure 1. The electrodes are made from rectangular steel plates. steel is mechanically robust to stain, good electrical conductor and is resistance to corrosion in alkaline solutions. A simple rectangular geometry was used for cell design. Each steel plat with dimension 13cm by 8cm was used for cell fabrication. For each cell 2 steel sheets were used. Plates are separated by using a 2cm plastic separator. The cell is used in vertical mode for electrolysis. in parallel set up. Inter electrode spacing was put as about 2cm between one plate and the other.

Figure 1 Cell for hydrogen generation

The implemented system is shown in figure 2. A semi permeable membrane is made using silk cloth to prevent the recombination of hydrogen and oxygen produces at electrodes. The membrane separates the cell into two

sections. The section containing anode collects oxygen and the other section with cathode collects hydrogen. Finally, outlet holes are drilled to each section to obtain the hydrogen and oxygen from the outlets.

Figure 2 Implemented steel cell for hydrogen generation

Solution Preparation

For electrolysis alkaline solutions are used due to the oxygen and hydrogen emission mechanism. Two alkalis, NaOH and KOH were selected for the optimal concentration performance. We prepared NaOH solution of 1 Molar and 2 Molar. Both KOH and NaOH was selected due to of its strong ionic conductivity and usefulness in speeding up the process of electrolysis.

Electrolysis

For green generation of hydrogen, the experimental was carried out by using as solar panel, a source of energy as shown in figure 3 the electrolysis setup can be used with and without solar panel. The panel generates an output of 21 volts which was down converted to 12V using buck converter.

Figure 3 Electrolysis setup with solar panel

Measurement

The measurement setup is shown in figure 4. Measurement was taken using a DC power supply of 12V and current of 2A.

Figure 4 Setup for Hydrogen Generation

Data collection

The experiment was carried by setting an initial voltage to 2.8V. The corresponding current and temperature was recorded as initial value.

Chemical Reactions

When we dissolve NaOH dissolves in water, it dissociates into its Na^+ and OH^- ions as shown by

Overall the reaction is given by

Similarly when KOH is dissolved into water it generates K^+ and OH^- ions

Overall the reaction is given by

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

NaOH with 1.5 molar concentration

The curve of figure 5 shows the performance of cell using 1.5 molar solution.

Figure 5 Current density vs Cell voltage at 1.5 molar NaOH solution

The cell voltage was raised gradually from 2.5V to 4V. The corresponding increase in current density was observed which ranges from 42 mA/cm² to 220 mA/cm².

It is evident from the graph that with the increase of cell voltage, current density also increases which in turns increases the production of hydrogen.

NaOH with 2 molar concentration

The curve of figure 6 shows the performance of cell using 2 mole solution. The cell voltage was raised gradually from 3V to 5.5V. The corresponding increase in current density was observed which ranges from 52 mA/cm² to 190 mA/cm²

Figure 6 Current density vs Cell voltage at 2 molar NaOH solution

KOH with 1 molar concentration

Similarly, the curve of figure 7 shows the performance of cell using KOH with 1 molar solution. The cell voltage was raised gradually from 2.5V to 3.2V. The corresponding increase in current density was observed which ranges from 59 mA/cm² to 216 mA/cm²

Figure 7 Current density vs Cell voltage at 1 molar KOH solution

KOH with 2 molar concentration

The curve of figure 8 shows the performance of cell of KOH with 1 molar solution. The cell voltage was raised from 2.3V to 3.0V. The corresponding increase in current density was observed which ranges from 45 mA/cm² to 193 mA/cm².

Effect of Cell Voltage on Electrolyte Temperature

Both the temperatures of the electrolytes were recorded during the experiment. It was observed that with the increase in cell voltage, temperature of electrolyte also increases. The higher temperature may cause rapid oxidation of electrodes and hence degrades the life of hydrogen gas generator.

Figure 8 Current density vs Cell voltage at 2 molar KOH solution

Figure 9 depicts the cell voltage vs temperature graph at 1.5 molar solution of NaOH

Figure 9 Cell voltage vs temperature at 1.5 molar NaOH solution

Figure 10 depicts the cell voltage vs temperature graph at 1 molar KOH solution.

Figure 10 Cell voltage vs temperature at 1molar KOH solution

Comparing the figures 9 and 10 it is concluded that the temperature of KOH based system is less than the NaOH based system.

IV. CONCLUSION

Two alkalis NaOH and KOH were selected to perform the comparison of Hydrogen production via different concentration. From results the cell voltage was raised gradually from 2.5V to 4V for concentration of 1.5 molar NaOH. The corresponding increase in current density was observed which ranges from 42 mA/cm² to 220 mA/cm².

Similarly, the cell voltage was raised gradually from 3V to 5.5V for 2 molar solution of NaOH. The corresponding increase in current density was observed which ranges from 52 mA/cm² to 190 mA/cm². The procedure was repeated for 1 molar solution of KOH, where the cell voltage was raised gradually from 2.5V to 3.2V. The corresponding increase in current density was observed which ranges from 59 mA/cm² to 216 mA/cm². Finally, we analyze the system with KOH 2 molar solution. The cell voltage was raised from 2.3V to 3.0V. The corresponding increase in current density was observed which ranges from 45 mA/cm² to 193 mA/cm². On comparing the results, we conclude that system with 1.5 molar solution NaOH is better than 2 molar solution due to its low cell voltage and greater current density. Similar conclusion is obtained for 1 molar KOH system. From results it was revealed that the optimal concentration in the said research is the 2 molar KOH with small cell voltage and large current density. Finally for longer life performance, the temperature of the solution is the parameter. The temperature of KOH based system is less than the NaOH based system hence KOH with 1 molar solution gives the optimum performance in terms of hydrogen production and life of the hydrogen generator.

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